

ESSAY WRITING TERMS

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract: Mazkur maqolada essening tuzilishi va yozish tartibi qisqacha yoritilgan bo'lib, unda essening turlari bir necha xil bo'lishi, yozilishi maqsadiga ko'ra uning qay turga mansubligi to'g'risida yozilgan.

Keywords: esse, reja, kompozitsiya, fikr, muammo, dalil, fakt, dalillar, xabarlar, turli statistik ma'lumotlar, mavzu, ko'tarilgan muammo

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Abstract: В этой статье кратко объясняется структура и порядок написания эссе, а также рассказывается о различных видах эссе, в зависимости от цели его написания, к какому типу оно относится.

Keywords: сочинение, план, сочинение, мнение, проблема, аргумент, факт, свидетельство, новость, различные статистические данные, тема, поднятый вопрос.

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Abstract: This article briefly explains the structure and order of writing an essay, and also talks about the different types of essays, depending on the purpose of writing it, what type it belongs to..

Keywords: essay, plan, composition, opinion, problem, argument, fact, evidence, news, various statistics, topic, question raised

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Essay to write in the process to the following attention to give need :

1. Introduction and final in part thought main to the matter organic dependent _ will be For example , login in the part "I'm about ... that's it If it starts with " I want to say " , it is final in the part "I ... to the conclusion I'm here " such as will be completed .

2. Essay feel- exciting / moving when writing and artistic likes paint from words is used .

3. Essay to the extent attention to give (from 200-250 words consists of will be Introduction - 60-70 words , basic part - 100-130 words , summary - 30-40 words)

4. In the essay only one topic around thought is conducted . In it only one thought to the middle thrown away and is developed . His one how many topic and one how much idea to be to the goal according to not.

5. Essay free composition based on is written . Good the essay the subject good understood him each bilaterally able to perceive , own ideas with the student to think can force only human write takes.

6. Essay in writing one in the mold from words use words abbreviated , superficial conclusion from release free to be need Essay language weight Demand does In this essay topic clarification , size and the goal sure set get important .

7. In the essay artistic fabric and fantasy it won't be . In it literary language from styles right and appropriate is used .

8. Essay compact voluminous because it is feedback in notification in detail from storytelling limitation is given information from the thread to the needle statement from doing preservation , one said the idea again to repeat the way not to put need From a long time long , mixed kind of joint sentences instead of short and compact expression method used ok.

9. Essay to paragraphs right separation need Essene writing after that , him repeatedly by reading exit recommendation will be done .

10. Encyclopedia and different from sources received data own in place application need without , write artistry and effectiveness defect enough

Essay in writing the following requirements strictly compliance will be :

- personal attitude to be notified ;
- thesis is the key the word right to determine
- factual arguments (arguments);
- to the theory justification ;
- terms own in place use ;
- quotes bring ;
- makes sense of legitimacy storage ;
- comparison and to conclude methods use ;
- literacy (methodology , spelling , punctuation signs);
- humor , sharp comedy;
- used scientific to sources links .

Sample reflective essay

Topic: Ecology.

I chose this topic to write an essay. Because natural disasters are occurring in ecology due to global changes in climate.

In my opinion, mother nature our to our help need. This is us the problem our coverage need.

International organizations by climate from o' change loss watching to the continents being given help and own in our area in the streets thrown simple one once water dishes or leave sent water packs secondary work to issue hand over and

live to our region and to ourselves financial help we give about the idea notice with essay requirements one did it we will be.

So , mother nature to save us own from our house let's start need I am like that to the conclusion I'm here , ecology to help needs and we him our rescue need ... the word

Argumentative essay example

How man in his life of youth importance ?

In my opinion , youth is this of a person to strength is full circuit. It is inexhaustible strength , enthusiasm , courage and strictly the will source .Youth years of a person unmatched creativity and creativity activity manifestation will be, society for brand new discoveries surface will come In this thread pencil vibration, I think , too a pressing issue because young people of society mover main power and are the heirs of tomorrow . Well , today young people own his life what with are they decorating ? Life, life content they are how do they understand? Your youth value they are how will they rate ?

Scientists « Youth lifetime of Gulshan Gultoji , " they say .

Here I pay attention of our ancestors life to the roads I looked will come Great our grandfather Alisher Navoi from a young age science to study, to a book love put Incessantly Readings because he is twenty eight at the age of perfect knowledge the owner , the thinker , the country known a poet and experienced , humane state character level reach received

The world peoples own science with to surprise Abu Ali Ibn Sina ten six at his age Quran Karim from memory knew and medicine to science sincerity leave it, doctor status received Like this people boredom of the era to the value get the opportunity g' animation know him knowledge and craft learning for those who spent That's why as a result universal level virtues from the line place those who received

Today own of youth value evaluate can't get people are also in our society just a lot. The time in vain to things spend doing young people in turn yet adulthood to his age not enough get up and get married cry in the streets by mistake those who walk how much " To the fullness." joy theft, robbery, mischief as a result black in the chair sitting , consequence of your life priceless the holidays fence behind to transfer convicted What about those who are ? Statistics to information than 18431 children inside affairs courts at the expense of received 619 of them are 14-15 years old between children 2035 people and 16-17 young people about teenagers. Above thoughts come came out without that's it let me say maybe youth each one to a person own understanding , perfection aspiration in life his own worthy place to find for to be given big is a possibility . So because we, young people our homeland the future our in our hands that we feel that it is necessary today's in society

position and our responsibility increase for each one minute g' animation As far as we know, it is irreversible of youth value right our assessment need

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